

Preparation of Silica Gel

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Silica gels of different densities were prepared by mixing sodium silicate and sulphuric acid solutions at different pH values, varying maturation time of the gel and controlling the pH of the maturation medium. Effects of the rates of drying were also studied. Effects on the mechanical strength of the gel beads on subsequent heat treatment of the dried beads were noted. Water absorption capacity and pore size determination was done according to I.S.I. specifications. Indicator addition was tried in the (a) acid mix, (b) silicate mix, (c) wet gel and (d) dried beads, and the most effective method was found out. Effect of copolymerization with alumina and Boron trioxide was qualitatively studied. A discussion on the existing literature and recent patents is also included in this paper.

SILICA gel is widely used as a desiccant for the drying of liquids and gases. Its porous structure, coupled with its avidity for polar molecules, also makes it suitable for the separation of polar gases or liquids from non-polar ones (e.g., olefins and acetylenes from petroleum distillation products). It is also used both in adsorption and vapour phase chromatography. Low and intermediate density silica gels are used as fillers in paper and rubber industry, in the composition of certain greases, in cosmetic and pharmaceutical formulations, and as catalyst carriers or catalysts in various hetero-phasic reactions. They also find use as abrasives and in the composition of certain cements.

The processes for the manufacture of silica gel involve (a) mixing of sodium silicate (meta) solution with a solution of sulphuric acid at an appropriate pH, so that a hydrosol is formed at first, which sets to a rigid gel on standing. This is washed free of electrolytes, dried and activated by thermal process; (b) The sodium silicate and acid are mixed at such a silica content and pH that a gelatinous precipitate is formed, which is washed free of electrolytes and dried by rapid spray drying¹⁻⁵. Some of the recent patents give the process of production as follows :

A Japanese patent, due to Sugahara *et al.*⁶, for the Mizusawa Chemical Industry Co. Ltd., Japan, outlines a process for the manufacture of high performance silica gel. In a typical recipe, a sodium silicate solution containing 60 gms of SiO₂/lit is prepared. One litre of this silicate solution is poured into 200 mls of a solution containing 85 gms of sulphuric acid/lit and 29 gms of aluminium sulphate/lit. The silica sol, so prepared, contains 50 SiO₂, 25 Al₂O₃ and 50 gms /lit of H₂SO₄. The solution is filled into a glass vessel upto a depth not exceeding 5 mm and evaporated at 90°. After about 1½ hours, the dehydrated gel is washed, dried and crushed. The authors claim excellent moisture absorption properties for the product, especially at high humidities.

A Czech patent, due to Adamec⁷ recommends the addition of an aqueous solution of sodium silicate (density, 1.33) to 9% sulphuric acid from a feeder which distributes the solution in drops uniformly over the surface. The individual drops change in the acid medium to ring shaped particles of silica gel which drop to the bottom until the reservoir is filled with the gel. An excess of acid is necessary. The process is claimed to give high purity silica gel, free from metallic salts.

A French patent due to Winyall *et al.*⁸ describes a method for the preparation of small grain silica gel. In this, 3 lit. of 6% H₂SO₄ are poured into 4 lit. of 20% sodium silicate solution (SiO₂ 6%, 2% Na₂O). The resulting hydrosol has a pH 10.7 and gels on standing. The gel is agitated and 5.25 lit of 7.1% H₂SO₄ added. The resulting liquid is sprayed at 400°. The product is washed at 60° with acidulated water (pH 3) and dried at 200°. It has a mean particle size of 35μ, a specific surface of 965 m²/gm. and a pore volume of 0.75 ml/gm. The free salt content is Na₂O, 0.009% and SO₄²⁻, 0.02%.

A Russian patent⁹ due to Sultanov *et al.*, describes a process for the improvement of the mechanical strength of the gel beads. The gel is roasted at 700°-1000° with a temperature rise of 5°-6°/min, with subsequent lowering of temperature to 600°, then the gel is treated with water and dried at about 200°. Roasting repeated in the final product at about 600°.

The main problems faced in silica gel manufacturing units are (a) Formation of "powders" during the manufacturing process and in handling, storage and transportation. This can largely be reduced by (i) pH control during gel setting, (ii) pH and time control during acid maturing, (iii) acid wash in the final stage, and, most important, (iv) controlling the rate of drying. (b) Improvement in water absorption capacity, which can be improved by (i) pH control, (ii) incorporation of some Al₂O₃ in the gel

(4 and 6), (iii) controlling the rate of drying and hydro-thermal treatment of the finished product.

In the present work, silica gel was prepared under different silica contents of the silicate mix, under different pH of gel setting, under different pH of maturing, incorporating B₂O₃ in the composition, using different rates of drying, and the effect of these conditions on powder formation and water absorption capacity were observed.

The most suitable conditions for indicator (cobalt chloride) addition were also evaluated.

Experimental

Commercial sodium silicate (meta) supplied as a solution ($\sim 35^\circ$ Be') in drums and commercial sulphuric acid ($\sim 45^\circ$ Be') were used for the work. The silicate solution was allowed to stand in vats for 2-3 days in order to settle the insoluble particles present and the clear supernatant liquid was siphoned out. Density measurements were done with a Victor Acid Hydrometer. Volume measurements were made with measuring cylinders. Mixing was done with manual stirring. After setting of gel, the gel was allowed to stand overnight to enable establishment of cross-linkages. Washing was done by filling the vessel containing the gel with water, with repeated change of water every 6 hr, until the

Water absorption capacity was measured as follows : The washed and dried gel was heated in a hot air oven at 130° - 150° for 2 hr, cooled in a dessicator; 5 gm samples were weighed out in preweighed petri dishes which were kept over 43.4% sulphuric acid in a dessicator for 24 hr. From the gain in weight, the percentage of water absorbed was calculated¹⁰.

In the "doped" samples, the requisite weights of the 'doping' agent (aluminium sulphate, boric acid, ammonium bi-fluoride) were mixed with the requisite quantity of acid, and then silicate mixing was done.

Indicator mixing was tried by (i) adding cobalt chloride to the acid prior to silicate mixing, (ii) adding cobalt chloride to the silicate before acid mixing, (iii) keeping the wet gel (prior to drying step, after washing) in cobalt chloride solution for 6 hr, and (iv) keeping the dried gel in 1% cobalt chloride solution for 6 hr, draining, washing, and drying again. It was found that procedure (iv) is most effective.

Table 1 gives the densities (as read by a Victor Acid Hydrometer), volumes, pH- of final mix, setting time, percentage of "powder" formed, water absorption capacity (I.S. specification, Ref. 10) and rate of drying for "undoped" samples.

Table 2 gives the above data for the "doped" samples and the nature and percentage of "doping agents".

TABLE 1

Sample No.	Acid density	Silicate density	Acid volume	Silicate volume	pH of final mix.	Setting time (mins.)	Water absorption capacity (percent)	Quantity of powder (percent)	Rate of drying
1	1110	1260	1	2½	4.5	instantaneous	30.2	60	1°/2 min.
2	1110	1160	1	3	4.1	1	32.3	30	1°/1 min.
3	1110	1130	2	5½	4.3	1½	33.5	15	1°/1 min.
4	1110	1110	1	3½	4.1	2	33.3	16	1°/1 min.
5	1160	1160	1	4	4.8	1	34.2	20	1°/1 min.
6	1110	1110	1	3	3.9	5	38.4	5	5°/ min.

TABLE 2

Sample No.	Doping agent and percent (1)	Doping agent percent (2)	Acid density	Silicate density	Acid volume	Silicate volume	pH of final mix.	Setting time (min.)	Water absorption capacity (percent)	Quantity of powder (percent)	Rate of drying
1	Al ₂ O ₃ 2%	—	1110	1110	1	4	4.0	4	40.5	10	5°/ min
2	B ₂ O ₃ 2%	—	1110	1110	1	3½	3.9	4½	42.5	7	5°/ min
3	Al ₂ O ₃ 2%	HF (0.5%)	1110	1110	1	4½	3.9	5½	45.2	negligible	5°/ min
4	B ₂ O ₃ 2%	HF (0.5%)	1110	1110	1	4	3.9	5	46.7	negligible	5°/ min

conductivity of the wash water was c.a. 10^{-6} mhos, and its pH ~ 7 . Drying of washed gel was done in a hot air oven at 120° - 130° , with arrangements to control the rate of heating the oven. Setting time measurements were done with a stop-watch. The pH measurements were done with indicators.

Conclusion

From a study of the tables it becomes evident that (i) a high pH of the final mix, (ii) a short setting time and (iii) a slow rate of drying impair both yield (more "powders" are formed) and water absorption

capacity of the product. "Doping" improves both these qualities, and the most preferable "doping agents" appear to be a mixture of boric acid and fluoride. Besides these factors, a short "maturing" time and imperfect washing of the gel also greatly impair the yield and water absorption capacity of the product.

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